

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This last issue of volume 1 of J.UCS consists of five high quality papers, most of them (contrasting to the previous issue) relating to more theoretical or fundamental results.

It is a pleasure to see how well J.UCS has developed within the first year, and how it has established itself as one of the major electronic publications in computer science. Note that this volume 1 of J.UCS consisting of 12 issues will also appear on CD-ROM: indeed, 30,000 such CD-ROM's will be produced and distributed by Springer free of charge. If you want to be sure to get one you may want to drop me a note: hmaurer@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at! But volume 1 of J.UCS will also appear in printed form as rather impressive book with some 800 pages. Thus, contributions in J.UCS have and will continue to have high visibility.

I would like to take this opportunity to thank all contributors for choosing J.UCS as medium of publication, and particularly all editors for their effort in reviewing papers. Most of all I want to thank the two other editors in chief, Cris Calude from the University of Auckland and Arto Salomaa from the University of Turku for their continued help, encouragement and support.

Let us now get started on the second volume of J.UCS!

Happy reading and all the best for 96, cordially

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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